

Complexes of 2-Thio-3-benzoylhydantoin with some Metal Ions of the First Transition Series

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Complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^I with 2-thio-3-benzoylhydantoin have been synthesised. Their structural features have been investigated on the basis of elemental analyses, electronic and infrared spectral data. The ligand field parameters *Dq*, *B* and β have been calculated for all the complexes. The ir spectra of the complexes reveal bidentate nature of the ligand and the electronic spectra suggest the octahedral geometry. All the complexes are paramagnetic.

In an earlier communication¹, preparation of the complexes of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with 2-thio-3-benzoylhydantoin and their structural behaviour were discussed. Now the complexation and structural behaviours of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the same ligand, containing sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen donors are being communicated.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand, 2-thio-3-benzoylhydantoin (TBHNH) was prepared by the reported procedure².

Preparation of complexes: Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solution of hydrated metal chlorides and the ligand in the molar ratio of 1 : 3 for Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} and 1 : 2 for the others for ~4 h. pH was maintained around 8–9 by adding dilute NaOH solution. The precipitated complexes were washed successively with water, alcohol and finally with ether and dried.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are soluble in DMF, chloroform and acetone, but sparingly soluble or insoluble in benzene and ethanol. The molar conductances in DMF of all the complexes are in the range 7.00–9.60 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ suggesting their non-electrolytic nature.

The room temperature magnetic moment value of 3.66 B.M. for the Co^{II} complex is less than the spin-only value (3.87 B.M.) due to spin-state equilibrium between high-spin ($S=3/2$) and low-spin ($S=1/2$) octahedral species. Some cases of spin-state equilibrium in Co^{II} octahedral complexes, viz. [Co(L)₂]X₂ (where, L=2,6-pyridine dialdehyde dihydrazone, X=I; and L=tri-(2-pyridyl)amine, X=ClO₄) are reported³. Magnetic moment value (3.87 B.M.) of Cr^{III} complex is close to the spin-only value for octahedral complexes⁴. Those of the Mn^{II}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes are in the range required for six-coordinated spin-free octahedral complexes⁵. Little higher value (2.00 B.M.) for

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Cl	μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	N	S		
Cr ^{III} (TBNH) ₃	Chocolate brown	245	7.30 (7.24)	11.79 (11.73)	13.48 (13.41)	—	3.78
Fe ^{III} (TBNH) ₃	Dark brown	324	7.80 (7.24)	11.73 (11.68)	13.40 (13.55)	—	5.85
Mn ^{II} (TBHNH) ₂ Cl ₂	Dark yellow	237	9.70 (9.30)	9.89 (9.58)	11.30 (11.00)	12.54 (12.15)	5.86
Co ^{II} (TBHNH) ₂ Cl ₂	Brown	340	10.35 (10.18)	9.75 (9.70)	11.21 (11.14)	12.45 (12.32)	3.66
Ni ^{II} (TBNH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Greyish green	283	11.28 (11.00)	10.46 (10.40)	11.96 (11.82)	—	3.14
Cu ^{II} (TBNH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Dark green	270	11.76 (11.52)	10.39 (10.26)	11.86 (11.65)	—	2.00

*TBHNH = 2-Thio-3-benzoylhydantoin.

Cu^{II} complex can be attributed to spin-orbit coupling^{6,7}.

The medium intensity ir band at 3 280 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{N-H} of the free ligand^{8,9} is found to be absent in the Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, suggesting NH deprotonation on coordination of this nitrogen to metal ion. Two bands occurring at 1 740 and 1 690 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ mode. The ligand contains two carbonyl groups, i.e. C₆H₅-C=O and -CH₂-C=O. The carbonyl of the C₆H₅-C=O moiety must absorb at higher frequency because it is directly attached with the electron-releasing phenyl group. The strong 1 740 cm⁻¹ band of the free ligand¹⁰ may be assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ of C₆H₅-C=O group while the 1 690 cm⁻¹ band corresponds to the $\nu_{C=O}$ mode of the -CH₂-C=O moiety¹¹. In the spectra of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, the 1 690 cm⁻¹ band disappears from this position and appears¹² at 1 620 cm⁻¹, whereas in that of Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes, the 1 740 cm⁻¹ band disappears from this position and appears¹³ at 1 710 cm⁻¹. The ν_{C-S} ligand band at 1 450 cm⁻¹ shifts to 1 420 ± 5 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes¹⁴. Thus in the Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, coordination has taken place through deprotonated nitrogen and the oxygen atom of -CH₂-C=O moiety, while in Co^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes, coordination has taken place through sulphur and the oxygen atom of C₆H₅-C=O moiety. The new ir bands at 460-630, 475-535, 330-385 and 300-360 cm⁻¹ for the complexes may be assigned to ν_{M-N} , ν_{M-O} , ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-Cl} , respectively. The 3 400 cm⁻¹ band in the spectra of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes may be assigned to ν_{O-H} of coordinated water.

In the electronic spectra (CHCl₃), Cr^{III} complex exhibits three bands at 13 800 ($\epsilon=16$), 18 100 ($\epsilon=18$) and 19 200 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=19.1$) corresponding to the transitions, ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) in an octahedral geometry¹⁵. The ν_3/ν_1 ratio (1.31) also confirms the octahedral geometry for the complex. The 10Dq, B and β values were found to be 12 228 cm⁻¹, 402 cm⁻¹ and 0.41, respectively. The lowering in the value of B from the free-ion value for Cr^{III} (1 030 cm⁻¹) suggests high covalent nature (62%) of bonding. The Fe^{III} complex exhibits three bands at 11 700 ($\epsilon=0.006$), 19 300 ($\epsilon=0.014$) and 27 000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=0.018$) which may be attributed to the transitions, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ (ν_1), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ (ν_2) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ (ν_3), respectively for octahedral complexes¹⁶. The ν_3/ν_1 , 10Dq, B and β values were found to be 1.7, 11 872 cm⁻¹, 742 cm⁻¹ and 0.56, respectively. These are in fair agreement with the octahedral geometry suggested for the Fe^{III} complex. The lowering in the value of B from the free-ion value for Fe^{III} (1 315 cm⁻¹) suggests covalent nature (43.5%) of bonding. The Co^{II} complex exhibits two bands at 16 500 ($\epsilon=1.6$) and 20 500 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=1.9$) corresponding to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow$

${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The ν_3/ν_2 , 10Dq, B and β values were found to be 1.24, 9 801 cm⁻¹, 891 cm⁻¹ and 0.79, respectively. These values are in good agreement with the spin-free octahedral geometry¹⁶ of Co^{II} complex. The low value of β is attributed to the high intensity of the absorption band and it is indicative of the coordination through sulphur and oxygen¹⁷. The lowering in the value of B from the free-ion value for Co^{II} (1 120 cm⁻¹) suggests covalent nature of bonding. The Mn^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 16 600 ($\epsilon=0.007$), 26 500 ($\epsilon=0.017$) and 28 800 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=0.04$), respectively, corresponding to transitions, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ (ν_1), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ (ν_2) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ (ν_3), respectively. The ν_3/ν_2 , 10Dq and B values were found to be 1.6, 10 500 cm⁻¹ and 700 cm⁻¹, respectively. These are in fair agreement with the octahedral geometry¹⁶ for the Mn^{II} complex. The lowering in the values of B from the free-ion value for Mn^{II} (960 cm⁻¹) suggests covalent (30.23%) nature of bonding. The Ni^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 10 400 ($\epsilon=1.00$), 15 600 ($\epsilon=2.00$) and 26 400 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=6.00$). These could be assigned to the transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) in an octahedral geometry¹⁶. The ν_3/ν_1 ratio (1.5) also confirms the octahedral geometry of the complex. The 10Dq, B and β values were found to be 9 801 cm⁻¹, 891 cm⁻¹ and 0.86, respectively. The lowering in the values of B from the free-ion values for Ni^{II} (1 040 cm⁻¹) suggests covalent (14.3%) nature of bonding. The Cu^{II} complex exhibits one broad asymmetric band at 14 000-15 500 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=11$) which is in good agreement with the absorption frequency observed in a distorted octahedral¹⁶ Cu^{II} complex.

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